

Technology and Policy Implementation: The Concept of Transition

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Abstract. The *concept of transition*, first identified by psychoanalyst D. W. Winnicott in 1971, "helps to understand that it is very often simply not possible to go directly from 'a' to 'b'" (Klein, 2005, p 202). Furthermore, Winnicott proposed that there has to be assurance "that the vehicle for transitioning from 'a' to 'b' has the *requisite characteristics*" (p 202).

Whereas organizational change is the action the organization takes to modify internal and external components and policies to meet changing environments, organizational change management is the method that is used to move those changes into action. Moreover, managing the change management process requires due diligence, flexibility, and adaptability before, during, and even after modifications are complete (Stobierski, 2020).

Accordingly, the *concept of transition*, first identified by psychoanalyst D. W. Winnicott in 1971, "helps to understand that it is very often simply not possible to go directly from 'a' to 'b'" (Klein, 2005, p 202). In order to achieve that goal, Winnicott proposed that the design of step 'b' is predicated on the thought and creativity in designing the vehicle for getting there. Furthermore, there has to be assurance "that the vehicle for doing so has the *requisite characteristics*" (p 202).

In addition to modifying components, policies are also subject to revisions. In this case, allowing the transition in new or revised policy implementation encourages "people to explore who and how they are in relation to the new situation" (Klein, 2005, p 202). Klein (2005) also refers to '*transitional spaces*', "where options can be explored in safety without repercussions, where people can experiment with roles and behavior beyond their own habitual ones, and where issues that the normal working culture may not encourage to surface can be worked through" (p 202).

Overall, in change management, the concept of transition can encourage alternative ideas to be generated, in view of developing "*human and social, or 'soft systems'*", while experiencing operational realities (Klein, 2005, p 202). Perhaps, Mary Parker Follett summarized the issue best: "We should notice too, what is sometimes forgotten, that in the social situation two processes always go on together: the adjustment of man and man, and the adjustment of man and the situation, in social-psychology objective reference is always two-fold" (Follett, 1951, p 122).

Discussion Points

Have the requisite characteristics been identified? Were transitional spaces encouraged and the results accounted for? What is the impact, if any, on the social situation? Was the original change process modified as a result thereof?

The following sections describe a few examples that serve as a foundation to understanding the complexities of developing a vehicle for transitioning from 'a' to 'b'.

Transitions During Crises

The research of Chewning and Doerfel (2013) proposed that "coupling chaos theory with social network theory to study transitional networks provides a framework for understanding crises as a natural part or organizational reordering" (Chewning & Doerfel, 2013, p. 41). Their paper proposes that transitional networks identify *requisite characteristics*; e.g. to "integrate several network mechanisms (collective action, resource dependency, homophily, and diversity) on several levels (network, individual, and link), at several points in time (development, maintenance, and dissolution)" (Chewning & Doerfel, 2013, p. 41). Chewning and Doerfel (2013) also found that structures go through a transitional phase during the crisis; and that this transitional structure may become the 'new norm' in the post-crisis phase (Zeller, 2016, Nov).

Hybrid Virtual Traditional Workforce Transitions

In the transition to / from the hybrid virtual traditional workforce, the challenge is that the vehicle for doing so allows for *transitional spaces* for roles and behavior to grow. From a management theory viewpoint, in 1924, Mary Parker Follett proposed that it is not where it takes place but to focus on the science of getting people to cooperate. Mary Parker Follett based the development of her management theory on the principles of coordination: (1) direct contact between employees and management to help organizations avoid conflicts and misunderstandings; (2) in the early stages, coordination should be learned and mastered; (3) reciprocal relationships / team efforts: regardless of their level in the hierarchy, everyone is responsible for pulling their weight and integrating with the rest of the organization; and (4) coordination is a continuous process that must be maintained (Caramela, 2018) (Zeller, 2018, Fall).

Expanding in the Global Market

Sometimes strategies are implemented without fully realizing the array of details involved. For instance, though Oreo cookies are a best-seller in the United States, the famous cookie initially failed in China. In 2005, Shawn Warren, a native of Kitchener, Ontario, Kraft Foods' newly assigned vice-president of snacks for Asia-Pacific was surprised to learn that the beloved Oreo cookie was "just a really small brand in China" (Beer, 2012). Fortunately, rather than give into the decision to pull the product out of China, Warren and his staff conducted surveys; hence, they learned to "adapt the product for local tastes" (Beer, 2012). In this case, the company was flexible in allowing Warren and his workforce to figure out what wasn't working. Then, they allowed time and resources for their strategy to be executed through their workforce. That is, by allowing for *transitional spaces*, new *requisite characteristics* were identified and change management, based on the new market, was implemented (Zeller, 2016, Sept).

Organizational Design Transitions

Renowned Contingency Theorist, Joan Woodward, conducted a comparative empirical study (1950-1959) of 100 manufacturing organizations in England. The results indicated that the "relationship between structure and performance surfaced only by introducing an extra variable: the type of technology" (Vector Study Group, n.d.). "In her later studies, Woodward (1970) emphasized how changes in markets led to product innovation which then led to changes in technology and subsequently organizational structures" (Hinings & Greenwood, 2017, p. 135) (Zeller, 2018 Summer). Whether change is due to technology or market developments, the issue identifies the relevance of *requisite characteristics* and supports the benefits of *transitional space* that allows for flexibility for alternative ideas to be generated while experiencing operational realities during the transition.

Adapting Human Resource Policies

Particularly during changes, Human Resource Managers can team with a wide variety of stakeholders to initiate new procedures to correlate outcomes. That is, in addition to creating a set of metrics that are basic to human resource reports; i.e. the required number of workers / productivity; Human Resource Managers can seek to create reports that link the changes to the workforce and to strategic initiatives (Zeller, 2016, Sept). In order to analyze the data, the vehicle for the transition needs to include multiple resources of *requisite characteristics*. Moreover, as with any human resource policy, the human and social, or 'soft systems' have to be addressed, as well.

Recommendations for Future Research

The recommendation for future research is to apply D. W. Winnicott's concept of transition specifically to management in the evolving hybrid (virtual / traditional) work environment. In essence, changes in policies as well as in the introduction of new technology or new uses of existing technology, affect the organization and coordination of the activities; e.g. managing how and where work is done, communication, and business processes. To complicate matters, in the transnational organization, managing change requires coordination across multiple regions (Zeller, 2018, Fall).

Future research may also consider Winnicott's concept of transition through a social-psychology objective where reference is always two-fold, adjustment of man and man, and the adjustment of man and the situation. Or, through Kurt Lewin's (1951) "force field analysis technique to distinguish whether factors within a situation or organization are 'driving forces' for change, or 'restraining forces' that will work against desired change" (British Library, n.d.). The "aim of the

'field theory' is to explore, in mathematical terms, the interdependence between group and environment in a system of relations" (Scott, 2017, pp.15-16) (Zeller, 2018, Spring).

Summary

D. W. Winnicott (1971) identified the importance of the concept of transition when changing from step 'a' to step 'b'. Moreover, Winnicott proposed that the vehicle for moving from one step to the next must have requisite characteristics; with thought and creativity in the development thereof. The challenge is to identify the requisite characteristics for development; then to allow the system which is carrying the design and development processes to be an open one allowing for modifications. In addition, time and resources need to be devoted for the strategy to be executed through the workforce with transitional spaces that encourage alternative ideas to be developed without repercussion. Nevertheless, modifying planned change process implementation should not be done with a haphazard approach; analysis and reciprocal feedback should drive decisions. All the while, not losing view of developments in the human and social soft systems; the adjustment of people and people as well as people and the situation.

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